

Climate Change and the Global Distribution of Wealth

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Wealth inequality dynamics influence economic and social outcomes and stability. While climate change and climate policies affect both physical capital and financial assets, their impacts on aggregate wealth and its distribution remain underexplored. Preliminary calculations suggest that climate change and climate investments could have substantial effects on wealth inequality, though the direction of these changes remains uncertain. This Perspective builds on numerical insights, outlines a conceptual framework and proposes a research agenda aimed at advancing the understanding of global wealth inequality under climate change, highlighting the need for interdisciplinary collaboration on the issue.

Introduction

Climate change and rising wealth inequality are two of the most pressing contemporary policy challenges. While significant progress has been made in understanding each individually over the past two decades, the interplay between them remains largely unexplored. This paper addresses this gap by investigating how climate change impacts wealth inequality.

The last two decades have seen unprecedented progress in measuring and understanding the distribution of wealth. Scholars from around the world have produced distributional wealth statistics, mobilizing administrative data, household surveys and national accounts [1]–[5]. Extreme wealth concentration has been studied from the point of view of its potential impact on the functioning of the economy or political systems [4], [6], [7], and from the perspective of economic power relations [8]. Access to a modest level of wealth has been shown to play a significant role in avoiding poverty traps [9]. Put another way, understanding the dynamics of wealth inequality stands out as key to understanding not only the functioning of the economy, but also the dynamics of well-being and power relations in society.

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To date, however, few studies have asked how climate change, and climate policies, impact the distribution of wealth. Instead, climate economists have focused on the effects of climate change on income inequality and poverty [10]–[17], revealing that it has been exacerbated within and between countries [18]–[20]. While income is a key determinant of savings and wealth accumulation, the effects of climate change on wealth extend beyond income. They influence physical capital stock, financial asset values and investment returns, which are critical components of wealth. Examples include agricultural land values, physical assets such as real estate or other forms of physical capital, as well as insurance risk premia [19], [21], [22].

While climate change may impact wealth, climate policies are also likely to do so, by boosting certain low-carbon investments, while penalizing carbon-intensive ones. Some studies have estimated the amount of investment needed to achieve the transition to a “net-zero” emissions economy [23], [24]. The impact of climate change mitigation policies on income inequality within and between countries and between generations has been analyzed [17], [25], [26], but not the impacts on the value of existing capital and wealth concentration.

Building on a nascent literature (Box 1) that underscores the challenges of effect identification and the absence of comprehensive conceptual frameworks, this Perspective aims to bridge the gap by proposing a framework for examining the intersections between climate change and wealth inequality, in alignment with existing wealth accumulation and inequality research. More precisely, we are interested in the following mechanisms: (i) climate events and their effects on wealth, (ii) the effect of climate policy on wealth, (iii) changes in expectations about (i) and (ii). Drawing on these insights, we outline a research agenda for the years ahead.

Box 1: The Nascent Literature on Climate and Wealth Inequality

Earlier studies have either investigated the impact of climate change on different asset types, or quantified global investment needs and stranding risks associated with ambitious climate policy. For example, several studies have found that climate risks - be they acute (such as floods, hurricanes or forest fires), chronic (such as sea level rise) or just expected - are priced into residential and commercial real estate [22], [27]–[38]. Another strand of the literature documents the impacts of climate change on agricultural land values [39]–[45], and related to that, on agricultural productivity and livestock [23], [24], [46]–[51]. Climate change also affects natural capital, for example through the degradation of glaciers, forests and oceans, as well as its profound impact on biodiversity [52]–[56].

Several studies also quantify the investment needs for a net zero transition [23], [24], [50], [57], [58]. An average estimate of cumulative spending needs until 2050 stands at USD 266 trillion [24], implying that global annual climate finance must increase by a factor of five as quickly as possible. Climate policies will also lead to the early retirement of high-carbon capital stock [59]–[61]. This could lead to asset stranding i.e. an unexpected reduction in future profitability of high-carbon assets, affecting their market value [62]. Such stranding could be substantial [23], [63]–[68]. For instance, depending on the study design, under a 1.5° temperature scenario, assets of the upstream oil and gas industries are projected to lose USD 7.3 to 12.1 trillion or USD 3.7 to 4.1 trillion in value, respectively [69].

Climate impacts and policies could have broader impacts on financial markets through changing expectations about the cost and productivity of assets [70]–[73]. Numerous studies document the repercussions of drought, hurricanes, and rising sea levels, on bond [74]–[76] and equity values [77]–[81]. Climate disasters can also curtail access to credit [82] and threaten the stability of banks across countries [83]–[86]. Past climate policies have been found to affect stock returns, the cost of equity, or the interest rate spread [87], [88]. To estimate the impacts of different transition scenarios, various studies quantify the exposure of bonds, as well as equity holdings and investment, insurance or pension funds to sectors that depend on high- or low-carbon assets [89]–[100]. Some studies suggest that the financial risks associated with the transition might become systemic [91], [101]–[103]. Studies also show that bold climate action substantially reduces financial risk relative to a business-as-usual pathway or a delayed and disruptive transition [85], [104], [105].

Wealth inequality has sometimes been implicitly addressed by discussing differences between countries in exposure and vulnerability to climate and transition risks [85], [106]–[109]. Studies that explicitly investigate the effect of climate risks on wealth inequality are rare. One study projects the impact of climate change on the evolution of the global capital-to-net-income ratio [110]. A modeling analysis of the Netherlands finds that climate disasters might exacerbate wealth inequality as low-income workers suffer relatively greater income losses, while the savings rate of wealthier households rises [111]. Another study directly analyses the distribution of fossil fuel ownership and infrastructure at risk of stranding [112]. It finds that financial asset losses primarily affect the wealthiest. A study that comes closest to our research question finds a substantial impact of temperature and precipitation anomalies on the distribution of material wealth of households (i.e. excluding housing and financial assets) in low- and middle-income countries.

The Size of Climate Related Wealth Transfers Could be Large

Potential changes in the distribution of wealth associated with climate change or with climate policies could be large. This question is largely left unanswered by the current literature. Yet, researchers are beginning to recognize the interplay between climate change and wealth inequality as a pivotal field for future research. One of the first papers to empirically address the question shows a significant link between weather anomalies and increasing concentration of wealth [113]. A recent work [114] provides preliminary orders of magnitude of the challenge by estimating the impact of observed climate change on wealth distribution and by projecting the evolution of global wealth inequality under alternative climate policy scenarios.

Climate Impacts

The existing literature on the distributional impacts of climate change has provided strong evidence for heterogeneous effects across the income distribution, both within and across countries. However, as income only constitutes one component of wealth accumulation, the estimated income effects do not allow for any robust conclusions regarding changes in the distribution of wealth. Hence, a separate body of work studying the relationship between climatic shocks and the distribution of wealth is required. A recent study in the field [113] uses a panel of 450 subnational regions from 52 low- and middle-income countries and finds that persistent temperature anomalies (i) impede overall wealth accumulation in these countries and (ii) increase within-region wealth concentration (see Figure 2 and 3 of [113]). Since temperature anomalies are set to increase with exacerbating climate change, these effects are likely to increase and cumulate over time if no significant adaptation efforts are undertaken.

While such results represent an important step towards a better understanding of the interplay between climate hazards and wealth inequality, they also illustrate the many open questions that remain. First of all, the analysis by [113] relies on a restrictive definition of wealth: Wealth is defined here as the 'material wealth' of households, which includes durable goods such as cars, but excludes other important assets such as housing and financial assets, which can account for substantial shares of total wealth, particularly for wealth groups at the top of the distribution [115]. In addition, one might be interested in effects that go beyond the aggregate. In the future research, we hope to have a better understanding about the impact of climate change on different rates of wealth accumulation between rich and poor countries, most impacted segments of the wealth distribution, and regions, countries or inequality regimes that exhibit higher or lower degrees of resilience to climate shocks.

Climate Policies

Turning to the potential effect of climate policies on wealth inequality, we focus on two key dimensions of the issue (Figure 1). The first dimension focuses on how low-carbon investments, and different financing options for these investments, affect the inequality of private wealth. The second looks at how these strategies also impact the overall split between publicly and privately owned wealth. Here, we rely on recent empirical work drawing from the World Inequality Database and on data on climate investment needs (see [114]).

The Potential Impact of Climate Investments on Global Wealth Inequality We first focus on possible trajectories for the global top 1% wealth share (Panel A). In one scenario, the richest 1% is assumed to make all required climate investments and own the resulting assets (Scenario A1, blue dashes). Under this scenario - keeping other investment patterns as in 2019 - the share of wealth held by the richest 1% of the global population could increase from 38.5% nowadays to 46% in 2050. In the second scenario (Scenario A2, red dots), it is assumed that all these investments are financed by a tax on the wealthiest, and then owned by the public sector. In this case, the global top 1% wealth share could fall dramatically, by around 13 percentage points, to 26% in 2050.

Another way to study the dynamics of wealth inequality is to focus on the public-private wealth split, that is wealth owned by the government sector and the wealth owned by the private sector [116]. A simple way to express the relative size of wealth held by these two sectors is as a fraction of national income, or GDP.

In one scenario, we assume that the public sector fills the climate investment gap between now and 2050 and subsequently owns the additional capital stock (Scenario B1). Under this scenario, the public capital stock to GDP ratio shifts from around 80% in 2019 to more than 110% in 2050. Conversely, when the private sector performs all additional climate investments (Scenario B2), its capital position rises to 216% as a share of 2050 GDP, while public wealth would stay at 80% of GDP.

Figure 1. Projections of Global Wealth Inequality Under Alternative Climate Investment Scenarios

Panel A presents possible dynamics of the global top 1% wealth share if the top 1% owns all required climate investments (Scenario A1, blue dashes) and if all these investments are financed by a wealth tax on the top 1% (Scenario A2, red dots). **Panel B** presents observed and projected values for private and public capital as a share of GDP. Scenario B1: the public sector (red bar) performs all additional required climate investments (compatible with the objectives set by the Paris Agreement) and subsequently owns the associated additional capital stock. B2: the private sector (blue bar) performs all additional required climate investments and subsequently owns the associated additional capital stock. Data from [114].

The need for more detailed analyses of the effects of climate change on wealth The estimations and projections presented here are, in many respects, preliminary and come with important limitations. Due to the mechanical nature of our projections, the policy scenarios overlook potential behavioral responses. In addition, climate policies may affect the distribution of wealth through many more channels than those studied here, via regulations, for instance, or through impacts on incomes, savings and capital gains or losses. However, these estimates suggest that the impacts on wealth distributions could be substantial. This, in turn, highlights the need for a more comprehensive examination of the possible mechanisms connecting climate change and wealth inequality, which motivates this Perspective.

A Conceptual Framework of Wealth-Climate Interactions

The above projections illustrate the potential magnitude of climate impacts on the distribution of wealth. Yet, the conceptual and empirical understanding of these impacts remains limited to date. In what follows, we thus propose a conceptual framework for the analysis of the link between climate (policy) and wealth (Figure 2). The framework relies on three main underlying

blocks (colored areas): the climatic risks themselves, how they affect production factors, and ultimately income and wealth. We begin by describing how they relate with one another.

Figure 2. The Impacts of Climate Change on Income and Wealth

Boxes represent economic categories. Arrows represent channels of impact propagation. **Climate and Policy Changes (First Block, to the left):** This block highlights two key drivers of distributional effects: acute and chronic climate impacts and climate policies. **Biophysical Impacts on Production Factors (Second Block):** This block encompasses biological effects (like impacts on health) and physical effects (like land or infrastructure damage) induced by climate change. It also considers the potential changes due to climate policies (e.g. in agricultural yields). **Monetary Impacts (Third Block):** This block introduces an economic perspective by monetarily valuing the impacts on production factors identified in the second block.

- Climate and Policy Changes (first block): Climate policies (whether mitigation or adaptation) are responses to climate change impacts, and mitigation policies impact climate change. Both climate impacts and policies influence the second block of our framework.
- Biophysical Impacts on Production Factors (second block): Climate change and climate policies have non-monetary effects that can be measured through non-monetary variables (e.g., health, material integrity, yield per hectare). We summarize these dynamics as effects on the production factors "labor", "land", and "physical capital", recognizing the role of these concepts in the analysis of monetary effects in the next block.
- Monetary Impacts (third block): Monetary evaluations, by nature, are incomplete, especially when assessing impacts on planetary health. Nonetheless, they are critical for understanding wealth inequalities, such as how changes in precipitation can affect land values. The impacts translate into tangible changes in income flows and wealth for economic agents, e.g. when the devaluation of an oil field due to stringent decarbonization reduces the profits for its owner.

We identify three channels (arrows) that operate between these blocks. We motivate them with the transition equation of wealth as it is commonly defined in the wealth accumulation literature [117]:

$$W_{t+1} = (1 + q_t) \times (W_t + s_t \times Y_t) \quad (1)$$

W is wealth usually measured in monetary terms, but, as discussed before, directly linked to the physical capital stock in the second block. Y is income - derived from both, labor and capital -, q is the rate of capital gains and s is the saving rate. From this basic equation, we identify three primary mechanisms through which climate change and related policy can affect the dynamics of aggregate wealth between time t and $t + 1$: First, what we call "Impacts on Quality or Quantity", which concern existing capital, labor income, or capital gains (W , Y , q). Second, "Impacts through Savings and Investments due to Income Changes", which capture behavioral investment responses illustrated through changes in s . And third, we also discuss "Impacts through Changes in Expectations" as expectations are likely to play a crucial role in determining the macro aggregates - in particular q - driving the dynamics illustrated in Equation 1.

- Impacts on Quantity or Quality (plain blue arrows): These impacts are observed when environmental changes directly affect resources. Climate-related events might destroy infrastructure [51], or the implementation of a climate policy could lead to the construction of new low-carbon energy plants [23]. Climate change could also affect the workforce, for example through climate migration, while investments in the renewable energy sector could create new jobs [23]. Similarly, the quality of resources can be affected, as seen when climate changes alter the nutritional value of crops [118] or when heat stress decreases labor productivity [119]. Moreover, one event can affect simultaneously labor, land, or capital, though not in the same way [120].
- Impacts through Savings and Investments due to Income Changes (dashed red arrows): Climate-related events can influence the saving and investment behaviors of both governments and households through their impacts on income that are well established in the literature [121]. For instance, households might increase their savings to compensate for losses in capital income incurred due to the destruction of their assets [122], or if they lose their job due to climate-induced economic instability. Similarly, savings might increase today if households accommodate the impacts of future climate change [123]. Governments might also change their investment policies, for example when climate change threatens their tax revenues from the private sector [124].
- Impacts through Changes in Expectations (dotted yellow arrows): This occurs when either households or firms alter their expectations about the future because of climate change and climate policies. Since financial assets are often valued using the present value of future expected cash flows, changes in expectations can affect financial asset values. For example, strong signals from climate policies (regulatory, informational, or tax-related) might lead investors to anticipate future cash flows from low-carbon energy assets. This

can occur without any physical alteration in the assets themselves. Shifts in market perception can also alter investment decisions. For instance, the anticipation of declining values of coastal properties due to climate change could decrease investments there [22], [125]. Lastly, the value of assets and investors' behavior might also be affected when climate disasters or abrupt policies impact the confidence into the stability of financial systems.

These channels are indeed intertwined: For example, the construction of new low-carbon energy plants changes the *quantity* of assets and may result of changes in *expectations* about climate policies. Nevertheless, we show that this framework is useful to structure the discussion on potential impacts of climate risks on public and private wealth inequality in the following two sections.

Climate Change and the Distribution of Personal Wealth

Climate risks are likely to prompt a redistribution of personal wealth. This is because 1) there exist strong disparities in the asset and income composition among wealth groups and 2) because the effects of climate risks are likely to vary across different types of assets and income, so that climate risks not only induce level, but also relative shifts in the wealth distribution. Put otherwise, looking back at Equation 1, climate change and climate policies might affect q_t , s_t , Y_t , and W_t , differently across wealth groups. To show this we extend our framework by showing the composition of assets and income across different wealth brackets (Figure 3). We then argue that the magnitude of climate risk indeed diverges based on the nature of asset and income categories.

Starting with the impacts of climate risks on the assets held by households, we associate the bottom 50%, middle 40%, next 9% and top 1% wealth groups across the US, UK, Germany and France with the assets that predominately contribute to their gross wealth (at the bottom of Figure 3). We thereby distinguish between housing, other non-financial assets such as business assets, deposits, pensions and other financial assets such as equity. There are indeed substantial differences in the asset portfolios of different wealth groups, with the bottom 50% owning deposits and housing assets (despite negligible total wealth), the middle 40% being largely dependent on housing and the top 1% essentially owning financial assets.

These portfolio composition differences imply that the distributional effects of climate risks hinge on the magnitude of their impact on the different asset types. For example, climate change might particularly affect physical assets like housing and agricultural land through the first channel described in Figure 2. Consequently, these impacts might disproportionately affect households situated in the middle of the wealth distribution.

Climate policies, at the same time, will not only require measures to improve energy efficiency of houses, but will also impact financial assets that are linked to high-carbon or low-carbon sectors.

Figure 3. The Effects of Climate Change on the Distribution Private Wealth

This figure illustrates how the distribution of income and wealth could be affected due to differences in the composition of income and wealth across the distribution. Values are based on averages from a set of rich countries (US, FR, GB, DE). The top left panel shows the distribution of labor and capital income by wealth group, showing that the bottom 10% of the distribution makes just 2% of total labor income and 1% of total capital income. The top right panel presents the distribution of wealth, revealing that the top 10% (yellow and orange bar) owns on average 64% of wealth in the countries considered, and the top 1% (yellow bar) owns 27% of the total. The bottom left panel presents the composition of income sources by wealth group, revealing the next "9%" (the wealth group between the middle 40% and the top 1% of the distribution) makes on average 71% of its incomes from labor incomes, and the rest from capital incomes. The bottom right panel shows the different composition of assets of various groups. The assets of the middle 40% of the population is composed of 60% of housing. Data from the World Inequality Database and [115].

Such an effect could significantly impact wealth owners at the upper parts of the distribution, who own most of financial assets. This hypothesis is in line with existing work showing that fossil fuel assets and infrastructure susceptible to stranding are predominantly concentrated among the wealthiest segments of the distribution [112]. Following this logic, climate-induced financial instability could particularly affect wealthier households as well. At the same time, economic turmoil could also affect deposits through "second-round effects", which constitute an important share of wealth for the bottom half of the distribution.

More complexity is added by the fact that climate risks can have heterogeneous effects on similar assets held in different wealth groups or in different regions. Housing, for example, is particularly affected in areas with high exposures to floods and wildfires, and there exists evidence that high-income home owners more actively avoid flood risks [126]–[129]. Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that the negative impact of flooding on W_t (Equation 1) through housing assets is more pronounced for households in the Bottom 50% wealth group than for those in the Top 10% wealth group. In general, wealthier households have more resources to invest in adaptation, although variations across countries remain understudied. Effects on other non-financial assets also vary by regions: For instance, the agricultural sector will benefit from global warming in some countries, while it will suffer considerably in others [51].

The effects on the different wealth groups also substantially hinge on governmental responses as well as the insurance coverage of affected assets, which is closely linked to expectation changes

captured in our third channel. It seems reasonable to assume that wealthier households have better access to climate insurances, and it will therefore be crucial to systematically study the ownership patterns of covered and uncovered assets.

One should also be aware that the capacity to react to climate impacts on wealth is very unequally distributed across households. In Figure 3 we present the ratios of debt to gross wealth by deciles for the US, UK, Germany and France. Unsurprisingly, households at the bottom part of the wealth distribution are indebted to a much larger extent than their richer counterparts, which exacerbates their vulnerability to climate-related shocks. Existing literature shows, for example, that access to credit is increasingly constrained following natural disasters [82], which decreases the resilience of affected households [130], particularly of those who were already subject to tight credit constraints before climate shocks.

Let us now move from direct effects of climate impacts and related policies on wealth to income effects. Income can be directly affected by climate risks (first channel) and in turn influence individuals' saving and investment behavior (second channel), thereby altering long-term wealth accumulation (Figure 2).

Numerous studies highlight the unequal effects of climate scenarios on household labor income, both between and within countries. For example, it is shown that anomalies caused by climate change have a much stronger impact on the bottom income shares in high-agricultural-intensity countries [18]. Hence, lower-income households - who in most cases also own much less wealth than their richer counterparts - might start to sell a relatively greater part of their assets in order to compensate for the income loss (i.e., incomes Y and savings rates s of different wealth groups are unequally affected).

Similarly, some forms of climate policies (e.g. carbon taxes) might particularly affect the income, and through that the incentives to save, of low-skilled workers at the bottom end of the wealth distribution whose jobs are at risk of being lost in the transition. This is supported by well-established evidence that market-based environmental policies such as carbon taxes without accompanying revenue recycling schemes are regressive, at least in developed countries [15]. Given the overall importance of labor income in the income of less wealthy people, we therefore hypothesize that the impact of climate risks through this channel may, all else being equal, increase inequality in personal wealth.

Investments in low-carbon assets might impact the labor demand heterogeneously too. The development of low-carbon technologies could, for example, increase the number of jobs in "high-skilled" sectors such as engineering, as is suggested by the literature on innovation, technological progress and inequality [131]. But labor demand might also increase in other sectors such as the manufacturing, installation, maintenance, and operation of renewable energy infrastructure, or organic agriculture.

To summarize, climate risks impacts on asset prices and the inequality in capital income remain unclear, but could be substantial. To clarify these, more analyses on the magnitudes of the

effects on different asset types held by different wealth groups will be needed, as well as on the role of insurance coverage and access to credit in shaping resilience to climate-related shocks.

It is also noteworthy that a significant proportion of the preceding discourse draws upon data and studies pertaining to countries within the "Global North" due to their accessibility. In relatively disadvantaged countries, where a significant portion of the population holds little to no wealth, climate risks may have less of an impact on the overall wealth distribution. However, they can significantly influence well-being, such as by affecting the informal economy, altering mortality rates, or driving migration.

Our discussion on the heterogeneity of climate impacts across asset types also illustrates why we believe that the distributional impacts of climate change on wealth are presumably different from the effects on the income distribution which have been quantified in previous work. For a given climatic event (or climate policy), the impacts may be concentrated on different parts of the income and wealth distribution, respectively. For instance, wildfires could lead to destruction of housing assets, but have also been shown to have effects on the wage distribution.

Public and Private Wealth Inequality under Climate Change

The previous sections have emphasized the relatively limited understanding of climate impacts on the distribution of private wealth by climate and wealth scholars. Yet, private wealth is only one of the two components of total aggregate wealth in an economy (looking back at Equation 1, $W = W_{public} + W_{private}$). Hence, inequalities in personal wealth should be studied in the context of the broader inequality between private wealth and public wealth. Recent studies indicate a substantial decrease in public wealth since the 1970s relative to national income, while private wealth has markedly increased [2], [132]. If the composition of private and public asset portfolios differ, climate change and policies could impact the public-private wealth ratio.

The distributional consequences of climate impacts depend on which sector holds an aggregate portfolio that is (i) more exposed and (ii) more vulnerable to climate impacts. For instance, to the extent that the public sector owns more exposed capital such as roads, power grids or other expansive infrastructure, acute climate impacts might hit publicly-owned capital stock more frequently or broadly than the privately-owned capital stock (first channel in our framework in Figure 2). While quantifying the exposure and vulnerability of the public and private wealth stock is in principle an empirically achievable task, the question has not been comprehensively addressed in the literature to date – an issue that can partly be explained by the lack of congruent wealth data (which we further discuss below).

Climate risks also influence the distribution of incomes between the private and public sectors. This shapes investment decisions and long-term wealth accumulation, as captured by the second channel described in our conceptual framework (Figure 2). First, if climate change disproportionately affects the production factors owned by private versus public enterprises, it

will impact the incomes generated from these factors. Second, when climate risks alter private incomes or asset values, they also have repercussions for tax revenues. One estimate predicts, for example, that 648,000 individual tax parcels in coastal US counties will be at least partly below the relevant tidal boundary level until 2050, which has substantial implications for local property tax revenues [124].

Climate policies also have the potential to shift wealth across sectors. Straightforward examples are climate subsidies or carbon tax reforms, that can alter private rates of return and asset values. Related to the third channel in our conceptual framework, several researchers moreover highlight the potential of financial bubbles in low-carbon industries or asset stranding in high-carbon industries (Box 1). While climate-induced banking crises affect the valuation of private assets, bailout costs to stabilize the financial system amount to a transfer from the public to the private sector [86].

Wealth shifts can also occur due to litigation risks, particularly through investor-state dispute settlements (ISDS), which allow foreign investors to sue governments if treaty-protected fossil fuel investments are canceled. These risks rise with stricter climate policies. One study estimates that ISDS-protected oil and gas projects needing cancellation to meet net-zero goals could have a global net present value between 60 and 234 billion US dollars, potentially shifting substantial wealth from the public to the private sector [133].

In the insurance sector, the distribution of wealth can be impacted by a government's decision (or ability) to act as the insurer of last resort or guarantee compensation payments to those affected. In the last decade, private insurers have not only increased premiums for climate-related risks, but in some cases even stopped providing coverage against natural disasters altogether [134]. In the European Union, only about 35% of economically relevant climate losses are insured, with substantial protection gaps for specific physical risks in some countries [85]. The extent to which government compensates losses from acute climate impacts therefore affects to which extent the losses are borne by the public or private sector.

In summary, first, physical impacts from climate change may harm public and private assets differently depending on their vulnerability. Second, climate policy may boost or shrink private wealth with transfers to or from the public sector. The direction of these effects is heavily contingent on form and design of climate policies. Since climate investments are set to make up a sizeable share of all total investment over the coming decade (i.e. around 30% of all investment needs by 2050 according to some estimates), who owns the assets and earns which rates of return on newly created assets has the potential to substantially affect the overall distribution of public and private wealth.

A Research Agenda for Wealth and Climate Research

In conclusion, we propose several research directions that we believe the climate and wealth literature should address. A key question emerging from this work is: How will the channels identified in the framework affect different asset types and wealth groups? Specifically, how will climate change and climate policies influence the growth rates of these assets, the saving rates, and capital gains across wealth groups, and what are the implications for inequality within and between countries?

The existing literature shows that climate change and climate policies are already shaping, and will continue to shape, financial and non-financial asset prices and the distribution of wealth. Among asset categories, housing and land values have received the most attention. In contrast, studies exploring climate change or climate policy impacts on the value of financial assets and other physical capital remain sparse. Consequently, there exists little to no evidence on how the distribution of these assets might shift under different climate change scenarios (see Box 1).

A key research priority, then, is to develop estimates on how climate change has impacted not only income and consumption distribution but also wealth distribution. This research can build on methodologies already applied to the study of climate impacts on income and consumption. Such efforts will be instrumental to help wealth inequality scholars in understanding how differential savings rates, and rates of return on different asset classes, could affect aggregate wealth and its distribution.

This work, in turn, can facilitate the integration of wealth variables across different wealth groups within climate-economy models. Although incorporating wealth inequality into these models presents conceptual challenges, a progressive approach could be adopted—beginning with non-financial assets such as land inequality and eventually expanding to include financial assets across various wealth groups. Recent advancements in climate-economy models, which have begun to account for different consumer or income groups, offer a foundation for the analytical expansions we advocate here.

A further area of inquiry is to investigate the ownership structures of existing high-carbon capital and upcoming low-carbon investments, starting with inequalities between the public and private sector, and examine how different divestment, investment, and financing strategies have already influenced, and could further impact wealth inequality and, more broadly, power inequalities. Here, collaborations between climate modelers, economists, historians, political scientists, sociologists and legal scholars will be key given the central role of wealth in social relations.

These research avenues are undoubtedly data-intensive, making access to old and new data sources crucial. Land registries were among the first economic statistics ever developed, when land was the primary source of wealth. Statistical organizations, with the support of governments and other economic actors, could renew this tradition, expanding their focus beyond land to

encompass all types of assets, including financial assets, and develop comprehensive asset registries.

New technologies can help. Satellite data, for example, can be mobilized for assessing not only land, but also physical asset valuations [135]. Recently developed methods to link household surveys and wealth registries can provide further insights into wealth distributions at a very granular level.

Standardizing data will also be essential. Recent developments at the United Nations, including calls for a global asset registry in the context of a UN Tax Convention could become instrumental in studying the wealth dynamics. Other advancements, such as the European Regulation on Low-Carbon Investments as well as certain private-sector standards, provide frameworks to help structure such data collection and transparency around high and low carbon financial flows and stocks.

Ultimately, these efforts to expand theoretical and conceptual foundations, as well as to collect, harmonize, and analyze data, are likely to require novel collaborations between social science and climate change scholars, as well as with administrations, civil society and the private sector.

To conclude, we posit that these research avenues could become particularly relevant to climate policymaking in the coming years. A deeper understanding of the political economy of the transition can indeed help accelerate it. This includes more precise identification of the potential winners and losers of mitigation and adaptation policies, as well as the perceived and objective interests of various groups of wealth owners in supporting—or resisting—the transition. In turn, this could justify increased investment in research funds to pursue this ambitious agenda.

Inclusion and ethics statement

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data and code availability statement

A detailed description of the underlying data sources is available from [114]. The code for figures 3 and 4 is available from the authors upon request.

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